

Paschal Mystery: Experience of Martyrdom Today

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Do you wish to honour the Body of Christ? Do not ignore Him when he is naked. Do not pay homage in the temple clad in silk -- only then to neglect Him outside where He suffers cold and nakedness. Today when the celebration of the Eucharist in public is not allowed, the Paschal Mystery becomes all the more relevant for the cries and agony of Corona affected people. The Paschal Mystery is to be understood as the process of dying and rising, death and new life. If we look around, we see this occurrence all around us and in our own lives. The Paschal Mystery is not merely about our own salvation. It is a call to continue Christ's mission, which implies that all people know the saving power of God. The final event in the Paschal Mystery, the Ascension, marks the beginning of the mission of the Church. During the Ascension, Christ gives the Apostles their mission, "Go, therefore, and make disciples of all nations, baptizing them in the name of the Father, and of the Son, and of the Holy Spirit, teaching them to observe all that I have commanded you. And behold, I am with you always, until the end of the age" (Matthew 28:19-20). Soon after this, the Apostles receive the fullness of the Holy Spirit, empowering them for this mission.

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Paschal Mystery

Paschal Mystery is Jesus Christ's passion, death, Resurrection and Ascension. We learn from Jesus that new life can come from death, that we can find meaning in tough times, that there really is light in the darkness. It can be considered as the commitment by which Jesus glorified his Father and brought salvation to the world. The word "paschal" is the equivalent of Greek "πάσχα" (*pascha*), which is derived from Aramaic "*pashā*" and Hebrew "*pesah*", meaning "the passing over." (cf. Ex 12:13.23.27; cf. Is 31:5). According to the understanding of our salvation history, creation was the first pasch as there was a passing over from chaos to creation or order. Immediately after it we have the second and a series of them follow. The second pasch is immediately after the fall of the first parents. Abraham, the father of faith, is chosen to realize the new pasch. He accepts the call of God (Gen 12: 1-4). Following this is the next stage of slavery of the Hebrews and liberation through the intervention of Moses. Finally, the realization and redemption of the new pasch through Jesus Christ by his passion, death and resurrection.

Mystery in the context of Paschal Mystery is the message which was a mystery hidden for generations and has been revealed to his saints (Col 1: 25-26; Eph 1: 9-10). It is the realization of the plan in Christ. "The mystery is Christ among you, your hope and glory" (Col 1: 26-29). It is salvation in Christ made available through the ministry of the apostles. Mystery is the tradition of the early Church. As we

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understand, the Church celebrates the Paschal Mystery from the time of Christ's ascension.

Paschal Mystery as Service

We live in a world dominated by injustice. Cruel, inhuman injustice is pervasive. It divides humanity into the First World and the Third World, the developed and the underdeveloped countries, the rich and the poor, almsgivers and beggars. We find injustice in all spheres of life all over the world. It dominates people, dictates to them, humiliates them and turns them into a herd. Therefore, the practice of foot washing becomes a very relevant theme in the context of Corona affected world. The responsibility to serve the one in need is the task desired by Jesus who had the humility to be at the service of the others who were his disciples. Rafel Avila in his book, *Worship and Politics* says, "Jesus took upon himself the prophetic criticism of cultism and even surpassed it by insisting that he did not come to abolish the law or the prophets but to complete them. He began by attacking the formalism and verbosity of the prayers of the Pharisees and placed worship of praxis important."

There is a legend of St. Francis of Assisi. In his early days when he was very wealthy; nothing but the best was good enough for him. He belonged to the aristocrat of the aristocrats. One day he was riding alone outside the city when he saw a leper, a mass of sores, a horrible sight. Ordinarily the fastidious Francis would have recoiled in horror from this hideous wreck of humanity. The sight moved him to do something; he dismounted from his horse and flung his arms around the leper; and

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as he embraced him and the leper turned into the figure of Jesus. This is what Jesus is trying to tell us by the service he does to his disciples. The nearer we are to suffering humanity, the nearer we are to God.

Paschal Mystery as Memorial

Jesus told the disciples, “This is my body” and he also said, “You saw Me hungry and you gave Me no food” and “Whatever you did for the least of My brothers, you did also for Me”. What good is it if the Eucharistic Table is overloaded with golden chalices, when He is dying of hunger? Start by satisfying His hunger, and then, with what is left, you may adorn the altar as well. The temple of our afflicted neighbor's body is holier than the altar of stone on which you celebrate the holy sacrifice. You are able to contemplate this altar everywhere, in the street and in the open squares (St. John Chrysostom). Pedro Arrupe highlights this perspective in one of his conferences, “If there is hunger anywhere in the world, then our celebration of the Eucharist is somehow incomplete everywhere in the world.” In the Eucharist, we receive Christ hungering in the world. He comes to us, not alone, but with the poor, the oppressed, the starving of the earth. Through him, they are looking to us for help, for justice, for love expressed in action. Therefore, we cannot properly receive the Bread of Life unless at the same time we give the bread of life to those in need wherever and whoever they may be.

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brokenness, his poverty, his body being broken and his blood being poured out. Pierre Teilhard de Chardin expresses this explicitly when he suggests that the wine offered at the Eucharist symbolizes precisely the brokenness of the poor. In a sense, the true substance to be consecrated each day is the world’s development during that day – the bread symbolizing appropriately what creation succeeds in producing, the wine (blood) what creation causes to be lost in exhaustion and suffering in the course of that effort. The Eucharist offers up the tears and blood of the sick in today’s context when many people are sick and dying and invites us to help alleviate the conditions that produce tears and blood.

Christ Himself set the foundation for uniting our sacrifices with His for the sake of our salvation and for the salvation of others. He instructs His disciples, “Whoever wishes to come after me must deny himself, take up his cross, and follow me. For whoever wishes to save his life will lose it, but whoever loses his life for my sake will find it” (Matthew 16:24–25). The Church holds martyrs as exemplars of the Paschal Mystery because of the high price they paid in following Christ. We endure these sacrifices not on our own power, but by seeing them as extensions of Christ’s Passion. In prayer we consciously unite our sacrifices—even the suffering we do not choose, such as the suffering caused by illness or accidents—with Christ’s Passion and death.

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Conclusion

To say that the Paschal Mystery calls us to justice and service originates in Jesus who, drawing upon the great prophets of old, assures us that the validity of all worship will ultimately be judged by how it affects the people who are in need, particularly the sick and dying. And we do that, as a famous church hymn says, by moving “from worship into service”. We don’t go to the Eucharist only to worship God by expressing our faith and

devotion. It is a communal act of worship which, among other things, calls us to go forth and live out in the world. It is a non-negotiable challenge from

God to each of us to work at changing the conditions that cause tears and blood. The Eucharist calls us to love tenderly, but, just as strongly, it calls us to act in justice and love. Many nurses, doctors and health workers have dedicated their lives for the sick and dying. Many of them have done this in spite of knowing the fact that the disease is contagious and they are exposed to danger. In the process, some of them had to sacrifice their lives in service. Such martyrs have the experience of living the Paschal Mystery today. They have broken their body and shed their blood for others. God is inviting us to build the kingdom of heaven on earth. Victory is assured as the Lord assures, “See I make all things new!” (Rev. 21:5).